

References

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Ir Spectra of the Oxides and Sulphides of Triarylphosphines and Triarylarisines

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TRIPHENYLPHOSPHINE oxide and trimethylphosphine oxide are the only phosphine oxides for which ir spectral data are available in the literature¹. No data are available for phosphine sulphides, triarylarisine oxides and sulphides, although Merijanian and Zingaro² studied the ir spectra of some trialkylarisine oxides.

Experimental

The following compounds were prepared as described in the literature³⁻¹⁸ - phosphine oxides: triphenyl³, m.p. 156-57°, tribenzyl⁴, 213-14°, tri-*o*-tolyl⁵, 152-53°, tri-*m*-tolyl⁶, 110-11°, tri-*p*-tolyl⁶, 145-46°, tri-*o*-anisyl⁷, 216-17°, tri-*p*-anisyl⁶, 142-43°, tri-*m*-chlorophenyl⁸, 135-36°, tri-*p*-chlorophenyl⁸, 177-78°; phosphine sulphides: triphenyl⁹, m.p. 160-61°, tribenzyl⁹, 213-14°, tri-*p*-tolyl⁶, 185-86°, tri-*p*-methoxyphenyl⁶, 113-14°; arsine oxides: triphenyl¹⁰, m.p. 193-94°, tribenzyl¹¹, 219-20°, tri-*o*-tolyl¹², 150-51°, tri-*m*-tolyl¹², 169-70°, tri-*p*-tolyl (monohydrate)¹³, 89-90°, tri-*o*-anisyl¹⁴, 203-204°, tri-*p*-anisyl (monohydrate)¹⁷, 92-93°; arsine sulphides: triphenyl¹⁵, m.p. 161-62°, tribenzyl¹⁶, 212-13°, tri-*m*-tolyl¹³, 186-87°, tri-*p*-tolyl¹⁴, 170-71°, tri-*o*-anisyl¹³, 185-86°, tri-*p*-anisyl¹⁸, 108-09°.

Tri-*o*-tolylphosphine sulphide: A solution of tri-*o*-tolyl phosphine (3.7 g) and sulphur (0.4 g) in carbon disulphide (25 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. Removal of carbon disulphide gave an oily product which solidified on cooling (3.3 g); recrystallisation from methanol afforded crystals, m.p. 159-60°

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(Found: C, 74.9; H, 6.1. C₂₁H₂₁PS calcd. for: C, 75.0; H, 6.3%).

The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 21 double-beam spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

In view of the complexity of the spectra, the bond frequencies were determined by comparing the spectra of the phosphine oxides and arsine oxides with those of the corresponding phosphines and arsines along with those of the corresponding sulphides. The bands due to P→O and As→O stretching are very strong and could easily be identified. The P→S bonds are weaker but there was no difficulty in identifying them. But the As→S bands seemed to be very weak and in most cases they merged with CH out-of-plane deformations of the benzene ring in the 850-750 cm⁻¹ region (arising due to two adjacent free hydrogen atoms and five adjacent free hydrogen atoms)¹⁹. This made the identification of the As→S stretching vibration very difficult and in some cases impossible. So any assignments made will be unreliable. Table I gives the P→O, P→S and As→O frequency assignments made in the present study.

TABLE I—IR STRETCHING FREQUENCIES (cm⁻¹)

	ν _{P→O}		ν _{As→O}
(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂) ₃ PO	1182	(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂) ₃ AsO	876
(C ₆ H ₅) ₃ PO	1183	(C ₆ H ₅) ₃ AsO	883
(<i>o</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PO	1182	(<i>o</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₃ AsO [†]	868
(<i>m</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PO	1181	(<i>m</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₃ AsO [†]	885
(<i>p</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PO	1179	(<i>p</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₃ AsO [†]	884
(<i>o</i> -CH ₂ O.C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PO	1181	(<i>o</i> -CH ₂ O.C ₆ H ₄) ₃ AsO [†]	881
(<i>p</i> -CH ₂ O.C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PO	1182	(<i>p</i> -CH ₂ O.C ₆ H ₄) ₃ AsO [†]	670
(<i>m</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PO	1188		
(<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PO	1187		
		ν _{P→S}	
(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂) ₃ PS [†]	687	(<i>m</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PS	688
(C ₆ H ₅) ₃ PS [†]	689	(<i>p</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PS	685
(<i>o</i> -CH ₂ C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PS [†]	686	(<i>p</i> -CH ₂ O.C ₆ H ₄) ₃ PS	689

The P→O and P→S bonds in triarylphosphine oxides and triarylphosphine sulphides are seen to have stretching vibrational frequencies in the range 1188-1179 and 689-685 cm⁻¹, respectively. The frequencies are remarkably constant and substitution in the benzene nuclei does not cause any significant frequency shift. The As→O stretching frequency is in the range 885-870 cm⁻¹.

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